

Synthesis of carbon dots from rose periwinkle flower using pulsed laser ablation for white light photocatalysis.

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Abstract:

In this work, we have successfully developed a facile and green synthesis of Carbon quantum dots (CQDs) from naturally available Nithyakalyani flower (Rose periwinkle) extract as a precursor using one-steppulsed laser ablation method (1). As synthesized CQDs were characterized by X Ray Diffraction(XRD), UV-Visible spectroscopy, Photoluminescence(PL), Raman Spectroscopy, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopic(FTIR) technique and Transmission electron microscopy(TEM) techniques. Moreover, we have demonstrated that the prepared CQDs could serve as an excellent photocatalyst towards the degradation of the Methylene Blue (MB) dye under white light radiation. The degradation mechanism of MB dye could be approximated as pseudo - first order kinetics according to the Langmuir – Hinshelwood model (2).

Keywords: Rose periwinkle, Carbon quantum dots, catalyst, photocatalysis.

References:

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2. A. Messerer et al, Carbon. 44(2006) 307-324.